

Development of Wireless Water-Waste Elimination Device

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Abstract - Ponds, canals, lakes and shallow water bodies add up the beauty of any place irrespective of rural or urban world. With the growth of the modern era The rate of pollution of water bodies rises exponentially. This massive rate of pollution is disturbing the marine life and also the beauty of the environment. Even though the local government does perform certain acts to clean those, the frequency of cleaning is very low and the reason for this negligence is nothing but a lot of capital investment, slow cleaning process and unavailability of manpower. By this project it is our approach to Make the cleaning process of local water bodies much easier, cheaper, automated and faster. This wireless device will eliminate the problem of labor unavailability. This approach of this device is also for the concern about the health of those labors who used to dive in those he pool full of garbage and trash. They were likely to be exposed to various infections and barely had solutions towards it. Controlling this device is just too easy. This WIFI(wireless fidelity)based water-waste elimination bot can be easily controlled by smartphone.

Keywords: water-waste elimination; automated; WIFI based

1.0 Introduction

This paper represents a waterbody motion bot that can clean trash materials from shallow water bodies such as ponds, canals and rivers.

^[1]The local governing body indeed works a lot and spends a lot of money concerning the hygiene and cleanliness of water bodies. but this traditional method requires more manpower; hence this is often a risky, and time consuming method that often doesn't pay off the capital spent for it. By considering this all, the remote operated floating river cleaning machines are more efficient and valuable than conventional methods and also this is effective and eco-friendly.

^[2]This machine consists of a gear driven conveyor belt mechanism which collects & removes the wastage, garbage & plastic based trash from water bodies. As a result, the problems faced during collection of debris are pretty much solved.

^[3]With the constant rate of industrial growth, the problem of sewage water must be urgently resolved due to the increase of overflow of waste in sewers from industries to the surrounding environment. To overcome this problem and for betterment of human life the design of this waterbody cleaning machine is proposed. In the proposal concept, the manual work in drainage cleaning is replaced by an automated system. This developed system is designed in order to reduce the excess manpower required and to make cleaner India.

^[4]The serious threat

to nature that the world today is facing is contamination of plastics wastes in clean water bodies. Every year about 14 million tons of plastic waste are directly or indirectly dumped into the water bodies. Nearly 2270 species including endangered aquatic species are known to have been affected by plastic based floating water debris. This has become a reason for significant worry to the world, particularly the creating nations.

^[4]This device is mainly used where water gets polluted due to floating waste and so it needs to be eliminated. This model uses a conveyor belt mechanism to collect & remove the floating plastic waste from the surface of the water. This machine will eliminate the waste products from the surface of water bodies which will eventually reduce the waste in the water so that aquatic life is let still and undisturbed hence such problems will be reduced. The most important utilization of this device will be implemented in shallow water bodies such as in lakes, still rivers and other water bodies to clean the waste products from their surface.

River water is an important source of irrigation for farmers which in return provides us with the valuable gift of food. They also take part in maintaining the healthy ecosystem of nature and bring prosperity. We made this project to clean the river which was soiled by us humans in the first place. After successful execution of this project, we can eliminate the pollution of rivers which is very beneficial for our society. The conveyor belt is used to pick solid waste from rivers. Water is the source of life. It covers 70% of the Earth. Water is literally everywhere but very few available for us to drink. It is a sin to pollute valuable resources like water. When there is blockage in the seepage then a flood of water from seepage happens, due to which seepage water will discover its own direction somewhere else causing serious issues. Based on that problem, our device will ensure that no such blockages occur at all from the very first place and which will get us rid of a very big misery.

[6]Humans faced the arrival of a lot of new variants of skin diseases because of water pollution. So to reduce the water pollution we are trying to make a Water waste elimination system. A device which involves removing the waste debris from the water surface. Looking at the current situation of our national rivers, which are dumped with millions of kilograms of raw plastic waste, toxic materials, debris etc. The government of India has been taking actions to clean rivers and has already invested a huge amount of capital in many river cleaning plans. By Keeping this in mind, this machine has been designed to clean the surface of river water. Conventional methods use such methods that need a lot of capital and man power such as the methods of boats, thrash skimmers, manual diving etc and are deposited near the shore of rivers.

This prototype is designed and categorized in two parts. The first part is the motion part which is developed with the help of Esp8266 Nodemcu, an L298 motor driver and 2 gear motors. The second part is a conveyor belt that would help the device to extract wastes from the waterbody. This is very simply designed with just two gear motors.

Few advantages of this device are as follows:

- Can be controlled by wireless technology using WIFI(wireless fidelity)
- Can be controlled by any android smartphone

- Though a dedicated driver is provided ,freedom of IOT(internet of things) based softwares is always there to drive this device.
- Reduces labor cost and time
- Cheap and components are easily available.
- Prototype is designed by using waste materials

2.0 Methodology

To Design this a very simple circuit is build using esp8266 microcontroller.

An esp8266 microcontroller has an in-built WIFI(wireless fidelity) module which connects with any android devices this microcontroller also has digital pins with which we can input commands using arduino IDE software. The movements of the device were initiated and written in the nodemcu using arduino IDE.We have used nodemcu esp8266 for our project which has CP210 driver port and type B micro USB port so one must install a CP210 driver in their computer to use nodemcuesp8266 microcontroller One must have a decent knowledge about Arduino IDE to design the mechanism of this project.

The Nodemcu was further connected with an L298 motor driver whose role is to divide power in the gear motors based on the commands given by the user to the Nodemcu. Further the L298 motor driver also power the whole motion circuit yes, that includes the Nodemcu too.

The prototype comes with another part that is the conveyer belt part. It is nothing but designed with two geared motors connected and with few pvc tubes and a cloth to wrap it up.

Fig 1. Block diagram of the movement component

Fig 1 shows the block diagram of the motion part of the device which says that the nodemcu is connected with digital pins of L298 and receives common power which is also provided by the L298 driver itself. The driver is also connected with gear motors for its motions.

Fig 3. Schematic diagram for the movement part of the prototype

Fig 3. Block diagram of the conveyor belt

Fig 3 shows the schematic diagram for the whole working circuit of the motion part of the device.

Fig 4. Prototype of the device.

Results:

This project is successfully finished with utmost satisfaction. The project gives a clever plan on growing a full fledged utility fulfilling the person's needs. The device is flexible to control as it allows any smartphone to drive it . This device responded just as expected to function and it is successful in cleaning floating debris from water-bodies. The code has been tested and has given a positive output. The machine created successfully fulfilled its objectives. There is plenty of scope for further development in this project and can make this project even more versatile.

User interface:

A software is developed using MIT app inventor to drive this device. The software establishes a connection to the device with the help of its wireless fidelity module. the interface is very simple which points directions to drive the device using only pointed arrows displayed in the software.

Fig 4. User interface of the driver software

3.0 Prototype observation

NODEMCU COMMAND	Motor input without command	Motor output without command	Motor input with command	Motor output with command
Right Reverse	0.1v	0.1v	11.9v	11.70v
Right Forward	0.1v	0.1v	11.9v	11.66v
Left Reverse	0.1v	0.1v	11.89v	11.62v
Left Forward	0.1v	0.1v	11.9v	11.70v

4.0 Practical field experiment:

This project is ideal for water bodies with nearly no current or flow in them, that is, lakes, ponds, canals, sewers, and some smaller rivers. Also to keep in mind, this project is only applicable and successful in removing floating wastes in the water body. This project has successfully shown good results in serving its purpose of cleaning floating water debris.

5.0 Future scope:

The biggest limitation of this project is that it can't clean wastes underwater, not that it is not capable of doing so. This project is made budget friendly and we have tried to make it as cheap as possible but on further development, an FPV (First person view) camera can be installed with the help of any raspberry pi controller. This would give user an idea of underwater Waste and help them in locating them.

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